

The Effect of Employee Morale and Capability on Work Commitment and Their Implications on Organizational Citizenship Behavior on Skpk in Aceh Selatan District

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Abstract: This research aims to examine the morale and capability role in work commitment and its implications on organizational citizenship behavior (OCB). The population was all employees of the district government work units (SKPK) in Aceh Selatan district, Indonesia, amounting to 2,217 people. The sample was determined using the formula of 10 times the number of indicator variables, which amounted to 170 samples. The result shows that Morale affects work commitment, Capability affects work commitment, Morale affects OCB, Capability does not affect OCB, Work Commitment affects OCB, Work commitment as a mediator on Morale affects OCB, and Work Commitment as a partial mediator on Capability affects OCB. These findings prove that the model of increasing OCB in SKPK in Aceh Selatan is a function of increasing Moral, Capability, and Work Commitment. These findings also prove that this research model can be used academically in further theory development.

Keywords: Morale, Capability, Work Commitment, Organizational Citizenship Behavior

I. Introduction

In an organization, its members interact with each other in harmony and build a sense of togetherness. The knowledge and togetherness will encourage employees to work optimally and even give their dedication beyond the main tasks assigned to them. The behavior and attitudes of employees who are dedicated to exceeding the demands of the task are related to the term Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB). The benefits of OCB to the organization are that it can help increase the productivity of co-workers, increase the efficiency of the use of organizational human resources for productive purposes, and as an effective means to coordinate activities between employees and between work groups.

The authors' initial survey in 2022 on district government work unit (SKPK) employees in the Aceh Selatan district shows that OCB had not shown maximum enthusiasm. That survey also found an increase in extra roles inside and outside their work to work more effectively in achieving organizational goals, but it still could not be optimally realized because there were still some employees who took actions that did not comply with the rules/low motivation, ignoring responsibility and trying to work optimally. The authors' initial survey also shows that in general, OCB has not been well perceived by respondents (SKPK employees in Aceh Selatan) because the average number is 3.09 (3.09 < 3.41). Implicitly the employees at SKPK in Aceh Selatan do not yet have OCB in carrying out their official work. The low value of OCB on SKPK in the Aceh Selatan will impact decreasing organizational performance. To achieve the target that has been set, it is necessary to have a better OCB. One of the ways that OCB can be created is through work commitments or work commitments.

Work commitment is the involvement and loyalty shown by employees to their institutions. In general, work commitment is positively related to OCB. Research by (Allen & Meyer, 1990) concluded that affective work commitment is very close to OCB, while continuance commitment is not related to OCB. The result by (Morrison, 1994) states that among affective, normative, and continuance, the most dominant influence is affective commitment. The authors' initial survey provides that in general, SKPK employees' commitment to work in Aceh Selatan is not good because the average score obtained is 3.36 (3.36 < 3.41). This shows that there is still a lack of loyalty to the organization that is driven by employees, so it can be said that employee work commitment is still low.

The next factor is work morale. Employee morale is the rules of norms and institutions that regulate employee behavior concerning society and social groups both in the work environment and other environments. This morale is a standard of good and bad that is determined by employees with socio-cultural values in which the individual is a social member. The phenomenon of work morale in SKPK's work morale in Aceh Selatan is that there are still many employees who work not follow existing rules. Employees often do not carry out the instructions from the leadership

Baharudin's research (2013) concludes that employee morality greatly determines OCB. This result was agreed by (Rahiddin, Nelmida, & Antoni, 2013) and (Djati & Adiwijaya, 2009) who state that morals have a positive effect on OCB. This is also supported by (Deswita, 2009) who states that morals affect OCB. The authors' initial survey on SKPK employees in Aceh Selatan reveals that in general, their morale was not good because the overall average score obtained was 3.34 (< 3.41). This shows that the existing employee morale is still low.

The next factor is the capability of employees. A good and positive organization also has the role of someone who can work fully and seriously in increasing organizational growth following effective and efficient goals. (Fernandes, Pereira, Bem-haja, & Amaral, 2013) argue that capability or workability is the ability of an individual to think logically, rationally, and intelligently, able to adapt to certain situations. Logical thinking and environmental evaluation help employees come up with new ideas, making them take risks to create new practices and new ideas that help improve performance. The research of (Oemar, 2013) concluded that workability has a positive and significant effect on OCB. The authors' initial survey on SKPK employees in Aceh Selatan figures that in general, the capability is not good because the overall average score is 3.28 (<3.41). This shows that the Capabilities possessed by employees are still low and need improvement. Several previous studies have been carried out but did not use work commitment as a mediating variable that mediates morale and capacity for OCB.

II. Literature

OCB

OCB was introduced by Organ in the early 1980s, but well before that year (Barnard, 1938) used a similar concept of OCB and called it the willingness to cooperate (willingness to cooperate). Meanwhile, according to (Organ, 2015) mentioning OCB is individual behavior that is independent, does not relate directly or explicitly to the reward system, and can improve the effective functioning of the organization. (Huang, Wang, & Xie, 2014) stated, that OCB is a term used to identify employee behavior. OCB can be done anywhere, you don't have to wait in a large organization or organization (Putri, 2018) . OCB is a form of behavior that is an individual choice and initiative, not related to the organization's formal reward system but in aggregate increases organizational effectiveness (Hendrawan, Suchayowati, & Indriyani, 2021). This means that this behavior is not included in the job requirements or job description of the employee so if it is not displayed, it will not be punished. OCB indicators according to (Saleem & Amin, 2013). Built from five indicators, each of which is unique, namely Altruism, Conscientiousness, Civic virtue, Sportsmanship, and Courtesy.

Work Commitment

According to (Chairy, 2011) Employees who have a high work commitment are employees who are more stable and more productive so that in the end it will also be more profitable for the organization. (Armstrong, 2012), said that work commitment is about identifying the goals and values of the organization, the desire to belong to the organization, and the ability to try to belong to the organization. (Mowday, Porter, & Steers, 2013) and (Guay, Choi, Oh, & Mitchell, 2015) view work commitment as a value orientation towards work which shows that individuals think about their work, work provides life satisfaction, and work provides status for individuals. Commitment shows a strong belief in and support for the values and goals (goals) to be achieved by the organization. Work commitment can grow because individuals have emotional ties to the organization which include moral support and acceptance of existing values and determination from within to serve the organization (Supriyono, 2019) ; (Coryanata, 2014) ; (Luthans, 2012). For individuals with high work commitment, achieving organizational goals is important. On the other hand, individuals or employees with low work commitment will have low attention to achieving organizational goals and tend to try to fulfill personal interests. According to (Sopiah & Sangadji, 2018), organizational commitment has three indicators, namely the willingness of employees, employee loyalty, and employee pride.

Morale

Morale comes from the Latin *mores* which means ethics or morals (ethics), attitude (attitude), or behavior (behavior). Morale contains the teachings or provisions of the good and bad of an action that is done intentionally. It can be interpreted that morals are one's moral obligations to society or in the context of this research to the organization. The

goal of morals is harmony or alignment of human actions with the rules regarding human actions themselves (Djati & Adiwijaya, 2009). The term morale is used to describe organizational behavior. In business organizations, of course, this moral understanding is associated with work activities and is termed employee morale. According to (Hellriegel & Slocum, 2017), morale is as individual and group attitudes on their work environment and attitudes to work as well as possible by mobilizing their abilities voluntarily. In this case, it emphasizes more the encouragement to work as well as possible rather than just having fun. Work morale is behavior, views, and norms about how to work as a person or group. The desire to uphold the quality of work that underlies high work morale. Individuals who have a high view of work life will participate in inspiring in the workplace. Organizational morals are: "individual or group mental conditions that affect organizational human activities" (Atussahla, 2019). (Drafke & Kossen, 2012) say that employee morale refers to employee attitudes both towards the organizations that employ them, as well as to typical work factors, such as supervision, fellow employees, and financial stimuli. This can be ascribed to either the individual or the group that is a part of which the employee belongs. There are several indicators of work morale according to Juliandi (2013: 105), namely:

1. Less aggressive behavior that causes frustration.
Aggressive behavior that causes frustration overall does not occur in the sense that it does not cause problems at work.
2. Individuals work with a pleasant feeling.
Every employee in the organization works with a pleasant feeling.
3. Adjusting to co-workers
Adjusting to co-workers is good treatment from superiors and co-workers, where a sense of kinship in the organization is always maintained.
4. Ego involvement at work
The involvement of the ego in working for employees to be enthusiastic in improving employee performance by maintaining work attitudes.

Capability

A person's ability is formed by knowledge and skills, and good employees have a good ability in carrying out their duties (Wijono, 1997). Ability is an innate trait that enables a person to complete his task (Gibson, Ivancevic, & Konopaske, 2012). According to (DeCenzo, Robbins, & Verhulst, 2020), workability consists of physical abilities and mental abilities. Physical abilities are physical conditions, health conditions, strength levels, and the good or bad biological functions of certain body parts, while mental abilities are mechanical abilities, social abilities, and intellectual abilities and also involve talents, skills, and knowledge. Capability is the capacity of an individual to perform various tasks in a job. Furthermore, it is also mentioned that the ability of an individual comes from educational background and experience and recognizes his duties (Timpe, 2012). Work capability is a condition that exists in workers who are truly efficient and effective in the field of work that has been determined (Hersey, Blanchard, & Johnson, 2012). Capability is something that is owned by an individual to carry out the tasks or work assigned to him (Wijono, 1997). Based on the explanations of the experts above, it concludes that workability is the action of a person who can do work according to his knowledge, educational background, and experience in his field of work.

In the research of (Raharjo, Paramita, & Warso, 2016) indicators of workability include the following:

1. Knowledge
2. Training (training)
3. Experience (experience)
4. Skills
5. Ability to work

Hypothesis

In this study, the authors determined the hypotheses to be tested as follows:

- H1 : Morale affects work commitment
- H2 : Capability affects work commitment
- H3 : Morale affects OCB
- H4 : Capability affects OCB
- H5 : Work Commitment affects OCB
- H6 : Work commitment as a mediator on Morale affects OCB
- H7 : Work Commitment as a mediator on Capability affects OCB

III. Method

The study population was all SKPK employees in the Aceh Selatan, amounting to 2,217 people. This study applied the analysis of Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). The sample was determined using the formula 10 times the number of indicators (Ferdinand, 2014) which amounted to 170 samples (totaling 17 indicators used). The data were collected including primary data and secondary data. This study used AMOS software as the data analysis tool for running the test. And for the first test, confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was used. CFA is to confirm the measurement model. CFA in SEM needs to be tested first to prove the model fit condition. After that Structural test was used to test the theoretical model (Hair, Hult, Ringle, & Sarstedt, 2016).

IV. Result

The SEM was formed after CFA. Analysis at the structural model stage was carried out by conformity and statistical tests. The hypothesis testing provides the Critical Ratio (CR) value and its probability/significance (P) to see the causal relationship, as shown below.

Table 1
Standardized Regression Weight

	Influence	Estimate	SE	CR	P	R-Square
Work Commitment	<- Moral	0.270	0.099	2,972	0.003	0.462
Work Commitment	<- Capability	0.462	0.101	4,460	0.000	
OCB	<- Moral	0.321	0.062	3,247	0.001	0.500
OCB	<- Capability	0.100	0.082	0,925	0.358	
OCB	<- Work Commitment	0.392	0.061	3,730	0.000	

Source: Primary Data Processed, (2022)

Based on Table 1, the R-square for the Morale and Capability effect on Work Commitment is 0.462. This explains that Morale and Capability together can explain the Work Commitment variable of 46.2%, while the rest is 53.8% is explained by variables other than those in this research model.

The value of R-square for the Moral, Capability, and Work Commitment role in OCB is 0.500. This shows that the Moral, Capability, and Work Commitment variables together can explain the OCB variable by 50.0%, while the rest is 50.0% is explained by variables other than those in this research model.

Morale role in Work Commitment (H1)

Morale influences on work commitment obtained CR 2,972 with P 0.003. Thus, it concludes that morale affects increasing work commitment. The magnitude (showed by its regression coefficient) of the Morale role in Work Commitment is 0.270 or 27.0%. This figures that better Morale will encourage an increase in Work Commitment.

Capability role in Work Commitment (H2)

The capability role in work commitment obtained CR 4.464 with P 0.000. This concludes Capability affects increasing Work Commitment. The magnitude (showed by its regression coefficient) of Capability role in Work Commitment is 0.462 or 46.2%. This explains the higher the level of capability, the higher the work commitment.

Morale role in OCB (H3)

The morale role test in OCB obtained CR 3.247 with P 0.001. This concludes Morale affects OCB. The magnitude (showed by its regression coefficient) of the Morale effect on OCB is 0.321 or 32.1%. This reveals the higher the morale level, the higher the OCB.

Capability role in OCB (H4)

The Capability role test in OCB obtained a CR 0.920 with P 0.358. This concludes Capability does not affect OCB because the significance value obtained is > 0.05.

Work Commitment role in OCB (H5)

Work commitment effect on OCB obtained CR 3.730 with P 0.000. This concludes work commitment affects OCB. The magnitude (showed by its regression coefficient) of the work commitment role in OCB is 0.392 or 39.2%. This figures the higher the work commitment will have a direct influence on OCB.

Morale role in OCB through Work Commitment (H6)

The Sobel calculation provides the Sobel value 2.510 and its significant 0.012. This reveals work commitment is a variable that mediates the morale effect and OCB. Thus, because work commitment affects and mediates, and morale affects OCB, so the role of work commitment in mediating the morale effect on OCB is a partial mediation. So the Morale on OCB is not fully mediated by work commitment.

**Table 2. Sobel Result
Morale role in OCB Through Work Commitment**

Input:		Test statistic:	Std. Error:	p-value:
a	0.270	Sobel test: 2.51053801	0.04215829	0.01205473
b	0.392	Aroian test: 2.48517042	0.04258863	0.01294894
s _a	0.099	Goodman test: 2.53669864	0.04172352	0.01119032
s _b	0.061	Reset all	Calculate	

Capability role in OCB through Work Commitment (H7)

The Sobel calculation provides the Sobel value 3.815 and its significant 0.000. This figures Work Commitment is a variable that mediates between Capability and OCB. Thus, because work commitment affects and mediates, and capability does not affect OCB, so the role of work commitment in mediating the capability effect on OCB is as a full mediation. So Capability role in OCB can be explained through the Work Commitment.

**Table 3. Sobel Result
Capability role in OCB Through Work Commitment**

Input:		Test statistic:	Std. Error:	p-value:
a	0.479	Sobel test: 3.81592116	0.04920647	0.00013568
b	0.392	Aroian test: 3.78635755	0.04959067	0.00015287
s _a	0.101	Goodman test: 3.84618826	0.04881924	0.00011997
s _b	0.061	Reset all	Calculate	

V. Conclusion

The result concludes that Morale affects work commitment, Capability affects work commitment, Morale affects OCB, Capability does not affect OCB, Work Commitment affects OCB, Work commitment as a mediator on Morale affects OCB, and Work Commitment as a partial mediator on Capability affects OCB. This finding proves that the model of increasing OCB in SKPK in Aceh Selatan is a function of increasing Moral, Capability, and Work Commitment. This finding also proves that this research model can be used academically in further theory development. In the practical application of this model, we can map recommendations for the research subject, namely SKPK in Aceh Selatan based on the results as follows.

1. To create an increase in work commitment and OCB of employees, the SKPK in Aceh Selatan must improve employee morale, namely, employees must be able to adapt themselves to other coworkers.
2. It is hoped that the SKPKs in Aceh Selatan will be able to improve their Capability by providing more training for employees to improve their skills at work.

3. The work commitment factor is a mediating variable, therefore to increase the employee OCB of SKPK in Aceh Selatan, the work commitment factor needs to be considered and improved to increase employee commitment so at the same time will have an impact on employee OCB.
4. Because capability is not a factor that affects employee OCB directly, the SKPKs in Aceh Selatan need to focus on the strategy for this factor to increase to have an impact on the work commitment so it can improve OCB indirectly.

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